

Vulnerability of Asian countries to climate variability hazards: A fractal analysis

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ABSTRACT

The study demonstrates the use of techniques associated to a newly-developed fractal statistics in the analysis of roughness hazards by countries. Results reveal the roughness correlation between hazards and vulnerability is $R^\lambda = 0.9996$, that is, around 99.96 %. The findings imply that hazards induce a considerable roughness in the vulnerability of various Asian countries. Specifically, countries that are more exposed to hazards are the same countries that are vulnerable. These countries are more vulnerable to natural hazards because they possess fewer resources and mechanisms to alleviate the impacts.

Keywords: *fractal statistic, hazards, vulnerability*

I. INTRODUCTION

The World Risk Report (WRR) consists of an index, a priority topic and case studies. The index describes the disaster risk for various countries and regions. The main focus of the report is on the threat from or exposure to natural hazards and the rise in sea level caused by climate change, as well as social vulnerability in the form of the population's susceptibility and their capacity for coping and adaptation. The concept of the World Risk Index (WRI) is based on the understanding of risk from research on natural hazards and disasters. In this context, risk is defined as an interaction between a natural hazard and the vulnerability of societies. Vulnerability includes social conditions and processes that are reflected in susceptibility, coping capacity and adaptive

capacity. While adaptation refers primarily to the society's long-term strategies for change, coping refers to the immediate response to ongoing natural hazard processes. It is similar studies that assumed that a natural hazard or climate change affects a well-ordered society. The WRI takes into account that not only the natural hazard but also the social, economic and environmental factors which characterize a society- as well as governance aspects- are crucial in determining whether a natural hazard or natural event (floods, earthquakes, storms) can turn into a disaster (WRR, 2012). However, countries in Asia are more vulnerable to natural hazards as they possess fewer resources and mechanisms to mitigate the impacts. The study looks into how the roughnesses of the natural hazards in various Asian countries persuade

the corresponding variability or roughness of vulnerability of the different countries.

A hazard is defined as “a dangerous phenomenon, substance, human activity or condition that may cause loss of life, injury or other health impacts, property damage, loss of livelihoods and services, social and economic disruption, or environmental damage” (UNISDR, 2009). Hazards can be single, sequential or combined in their origin and effects. Each hazard is characterized by its location, intensity, probability and likely frequency. Typical examples of hazards can be the absence of rain (leading to drought) or the abundance, thereof (leading to flooding). Chemical manufacturing plants near settlements can also be regarded as hazardous; similarly, incorrect agricultural techniques will in the long run lead to possible disasters. Hazards can either be a creation of humans (anthropogenic) or the environment (natural). Although the former can be easily planned for than the latter, in both cases the management of the hazard will remain the same. Our development efforts and attention should therefore be focused on the presence of various hazards and this must inform our planning. A distinction should also be made between normal natural occurrences and natural hazards. Natural phenomena are extreme climatological (weather), hydrological (water), or geological (earth) processes that do not pose any threat to person or property. A massive earthquake in an unpopulated area (e.g. the Sahara desert) is a natural phenomenon. Once the consequences (a possible hazardous situation) of this natural phenomenon come into contact with human being, they become a natural hazard. If this natural hazard (due to the unplanned or poorly planned activities of the human beings) affects them and that they are unable to cope, the situation becomes a disaster (USAID, 2011).

Vulnerability is defined as the characteristics and circumstances of a community, system or asset that make it susceptible to the damaging

effects of a hazard. Moreover, vulnerability is a set of prevailing or consequential conditions arising from various physical, social, economic and environmental factors which increase the susceptibility of a community to the impact of hazards (UNISDR, 2002:24). It can also comprise physical, socio-economic and/or political factors that adversely affect the ability of communities to respond to events (Jegillos, 1999). Blaikie et al. (1994) are of the opinion that vulnerability is constituted by the characteristics of a person or group in terms of their capacity to anticipate, cope with, resist and recover from the impact of a hazard. In addition, vulnerability can be expressed as the degree of loss resulting from a potentially damaging phenomenon or hazard. It is therefore the extent to which a community will degrade when subjected to a specified set of hazardous conditions. Thus, vulnerability has some distinct underlying causes. The magnitude of each disaster, measured in deaths, damage, or cost (for a given developing country) increases with the increased marginalization of the population. This can be caused by a high birth rate, problems of land tenure and economic opportunity, and the misallocation of resources to meet the basic human needs of an expanding population. As the population increases, the best land in both rural and urban areas are taken up, and those seeking land for farming or housing are forced to accept inadequate land. This offers less productivity and a smaller measure of physical or economic safety, thus rendering the community vulnerable (USAID, 2011).

Strictly speaking, there is no such thing as natural disaster, but there are natural hazards. A disaster is the result of a hazard's impact on society. So the effects of a disaster are determined by the extent of a community's vulnerability to the hazard (conversely, its ability, or capacity to cope with it). This vulnerability is not natural, but the result of an entire range of constantly changing physical, social, economic, cultural, political and even psychological factors shape

people's lives and create an environment in which they live." Twigg (2001:6).

In this study, the researchers attempt to look into how the roughness of natural hazards in various Asian countries persuade the corresponding variability or roughness of vulnerability by using the newly-developed fractal technique called roughness correlation (R^λ) (Padua, 2013). They expect that countries exposed to natural hazards are more vulnerable as they possess fewer resources and mechanisms to mitigate the impact. Practically, it will present how natural hazards made significant contributions to the vulnerability of certain Asian countries.

II. METHODOLOGY

The data utilized in the study were obtained from online data sets. Using the hazards and vulnerability data by countries taken from the World Risk Report (WRR) 2012, the fractal dimensions of the two variables were determined.

The fractal dimensions of the two (2) variables, the hazards (x) and vulnerability (y), were obtained by transforming the data sets into graphs. The one-dimensional representation of the variables in question tells how a straight line segment is fragmented by the random variable in question. The degree of fragmentation or roughness is summarized in an index called the fractal dimension (λ). The fractal dimension is calculated through the box-counting method which is automated through the freeware fractal software.

The result of two-dimensional configuration (x,y) will tell a fractal figure. The fractal dimension of this two-dimensional configuration is likewise obtained by the box-counting algorithm using the *frak.out software*.

In this paper, it investigates how the fractal dimension of the two (2) variables correlate with each other. The results will look into how the roughness of the hazards in various Asian countries influence the corresponding

variability or roughness of vulnerability and the formula is as follows:

$$R^\lambda = 1 - (\lambda - 1) \sqrt{\lambda_x \lambda_y}$$

Where:

λ = fractal dimension of scatter plot

λ_x = fractal dimension of X

λ_y = fractal dimension of Y

R^λ = roughness correlation

III. RESULTS

Figure 1 illustrates the fragmentation induced by hazard on the smoothness of the natural hazards on various Asian countries.

Figure 1: Fragmentation or fractality induced by hazard on various Asian countries.

As seen, fragmentations of the hazard data are obvious on the other side ends. These mean that variations of hazard are found among countries with the highest variation, either increase or decrease. The countries that are most exposed to hazards are the Philippines, Japan, Brunei, Bangladesh, Cambodia, East Timor, Vietnam, Indonesia, Kyrgyzstan and Burma while countries that are not exposed to hazards are Qatar, Saudi Arabia, Bahrain, UAE, Oman, Israel, Mongolia, Singapore, Iraq, Kuwait and Yemen. Then the researchers computed the dimension of this graph of which the resulting λ_y is equal to 1.5636. This supports the initial observation on the graph that the data set shows fractality; that is, the data are far more rugged than a straight line. The fractal spectrum is displayed for a deeper analysis of the situation:

Figure 2. Fractal Spectrum of the Hazard

The spectrum shows multi rather than mono-fractal observations. For countries belonging to the smaller scale, low fractal dimensions are noted while for countries belonging to the larger scale, high fractal dimensions are observed.

In other words, the researchers observe greater variability in the hazard for countries with higher hazards scores i.e. countries which are generally exposed are more variant in terms of the hazard. In contrast, least exposed countries are relatively more homogeneous in terms of this index since their fractal dimensions are lower.

Figure 3. Fragmentation or fractality induced by vulnerability of various Asian countries.

The graph of the data on vulnerability is shown in Figure 3. The fragmentation of the data is evident on opposite ends, specifically among countries that are vulnerable. These countries include East Timor; Yemen, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Nepal, Cambodia, Burma, Iraq, India and Laos while countries that are resilient are Japan, Singapore, UAE, Qatar, Israel, Brunie, Kuwait, Bahrain, Kazakhstan, Oman and Saudi Arabia. The computed fractal dimension of this graph is

$\Lambda_x = 1.4983$ which is less rugged than the previous data set.

Figure 4. Fractal Spectrum of the vulnerability by countries.

The spectrum shows multi rather than mono-fractal observations. For countries belonging to the smaller scale have high fractal dimension while for countries belonging to the larger scale have low fractal dimension. To be exact, we observe greater consistency for countries with larger vulnerability score.

Figure 5. Plot of hazards versus vulnerability by countries, $\Delta_{xy} = 1.0050$.

Figure 5 presents the plot of the relationship between hazard versus vulnerability by countries. The plot has a fractal dimension of $\Lambda_x = 1.0050$. As seen from the plot, there is no visible relationship if we use classical statistics. Let us now turn to a complimentary statistics called roughness correlation, load the fractal dimension values to its formula and find out if the roughness or variations in hazard is induced by the roughness in vulnerability of various Asian countries.

Roughness correlation (R^λ) between two

variables reveals the degree of roughness induced on the dependent variable by the independent variable. If its value is $R^2 = 1$, there is a perfect roughness correlation; that is, the roughness or variation in the independent variable perfectly induces the roughness in the dependent variable. On the other hand, $R^2 = 0$ implies the absence of roughness correlation. The roughness correlation between hazard and vulnerability is $R^2 = 0.9996$, that is, around 99.96 %. Thus, it follows that hazard induce a considerable roughness in the vulnerability of various Asian countries.

IV. DISCUSSION

In the study, the researchers attempted to use roughness correlation in the analysis of the ruggedness in hazard use induced by the corresponding ruggedness of vulnerability by different Asian countries. Indeed, high scores in hazard cause the increase in the levels of vulnerability by countries. However, they admitted that current measurement of the variables may not be comprehensive enough. Other variables could be used to replace or add the current exposure to hazard and vulnerability by countries. For example, mitigation and other measures of levels of coping mechanism to disaster can be used to measure the vulnerability. Nevertheless, current literature offers evidence that to some extent hazards cause the rise in the levels of vulnerability.

The researchers situate the current findings in the theoretical advancement occurred with the *At Risk* volume, especially the (PAR model) pressure and release model (Blaikie et al., 1994; Wisner et al., 2004). The pressure and release model (PAR model) views disaster as the intersection of two major forces: (1) those processes generating vulnerability on the one hand, and (2) the natural hazard event. The PAR approach underlines how disasters occur when natural hazards affect vulnerable people (Blaikie et al., 1994; Wisner et al., 2004: 49–86). In this case, the researchers have provided evidence that countries exposed to hazards increase the vulnerability of the area. In particular, the exposure of a country to hazards

somehow dictates the levels of vulnerability in that country. The framework stresses the fact that vulnerability and the development of a potential disaster can be viewed as a process involving increasing pressure on the one hand and the opportunities to relieve the pressure on the other.

Villagrán de León (2004) also explains vulnerability in the hazard and risk context. He defines a triangle of risk, which consists of the three components of vulnerability, hazard and deficiencies in preparedness (Villagrán de León, 2004:10). His figure reflects the “risk triangle” developed earlier by Crichton (1999). However, he defined vulnerability as the pre-existing conditions that make infrastructure, processes, services and productivity more prone to be affected by an external hazard. In contrast to the positive definition of coping capacities, he used the term “deficiencies in preparedness” to capture the lack of coping capacities of a society or a specific element at risk (Villagrán de León, 2001:4). Although, the term exposure is not directly mentioned, he viewed exposure primarily as a component of the hazard (Villagrán de León, Chapter 16).

The relationship between hazard and vulnerability is evident. For example, countries that are vulnerable like Bangladesh, Burma, Cambodia, and the Philippines etc. are also countries which are more exposed to natural hazards. Inversely, countries that are resilient are also countries which are least exposed to hazards like Qatar, Saudi Arabia, UAE, Israel, Singapore, Kuwait, Bahrain, etc. Furthermore, countries that are resilient to natural hazards are developed and well-off Asian countries as they possess more resources and mechanisms to mitigate the impacts.

V. CONCLUSION

The study offers evidence on the relationship of hazard to vulnerability by countries. The variation or roughness in hazards induces the roughness in the levels of vulnerability by countries. Countries that are more exposed

to hazards are also the countries which are vulnerable. These countries are more vulnerable to natural hazards because they possess fewer resources and mechanisms to alleviate the impacts. The pressure and release model (PAR Model) therefore supported that there are certain underlying causes, dynamic pressures and unsafe conditions which contributed to vulnerability. A key factor influencing the level of vulnerability in any community is the existence of hazards.

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APPENDIX

Countries of Asia	Hazard	Vulnerability
1. Azerbaijan	13.16	46.34
2. Armenia	14.51	48.49
3. Bahrain	4.27	42.44
4. Bangladesh	31.7	63.78
5. Bhutan	14.81	55.14
6. Brunei	41.1	38.72
7. Burma	14.87	61.57
8. Cambodia	27.65	62.07
9. China	14.43	48.83
10. East Timor	25.73	66.59
11. India	11.94	60.95
12. Indonesia	19.36	55.48
13. Iran	10.19	48.85
14. Iraq	8.08	61.2
15. Israel	6.41	37.88
16. Japan	45.91	29.46
17. Jordan	10.53	46.5
18. Kazakhstan	9.11	42.47
19. Kuwait	9.04	41.03
20. Kyrgyzstan	16.63	51.1
21. Laos	9.55	60.03
22. Lebanon	11.14	45.75
23. Malaysia	14.6	44.74
24. Mongolia	6.52	49.66
25. Nepal	9.16	62.19
26. Oman	6.41	42.48
27. Pakistan	11.36	63.86
28. Philippines	52.46	53.35
29. Qatar	0.28	36.18
30. Saudi Arabia	2.93	44.53
31. Singapore	7.82	32.47
32. Sri Lanka	14.79	52.67
33. Syria	10.56	53.81
34. Tajikistan	12.98	56.99
35. Thailand	13.7	47.03
36. Turkey	12.25	46.35
37. Turkmenistan	13.19	49.65
38. UAE	5.93	34.84
39. Uzbekistan	16.18	53.84
40. Vietnam	25.35	50.83
41. Yemen	9.04	66.13

